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Editor's note

Historically, people have found in art a form of expression not only for aesthetic delight but also to communicate emotions and feelings to convey ideas. From cave paintings in the Paleolithic to the most modern currents and styles of the different disciplines and expressions of art, we find a great variety of themes that commonly reflect the things relevant to society at a specific moment. Art has become a means to connect people and create a common language through which we express ourselves and seek to raise our voices to generate change. "Change" is one of the highest-grossing words of our times.

In this issue, we talk about ARTivism. The first note by Flor Paz, an Ideograma consultant, introduces us to this concept that combines *art and activism*; in the second note, Adrián Fernández from MeCCS explores how music has played a key role as a form of activism. In the *CO₂nversing* section, we present an interview with Jill Pelto, an artist and scientist, whose work combines art and scientific data. The "Yes, yes it is" section displays a "gallery" where Iliana Muñoz, Thijs Biersteker and Jill Pelto share their works for your delight and reflection: a story, an exhibition, and illustrations. Of course, we leave you a list of recommendations to *Take-away* that we hope you like.

INSPIRE AND MOBILIZE: THE USE OF ARTISTIC LANGUAGES IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL CAUSE

By Flor Paz

In May 2023, a group of activists interrupted the annual meeting of shareholders of Barclays Bank, one of the world's most influential financial services companies. When its president highlighted the bank's commitments to stop the climate emergency, participants from the Climate Choir group began to sing to the rhythm of the Spice Girls. They sang a cover of Stop Right Now with a catchy tone and some tweaks: "Stop right now, no more oil and gas. Stop burning fossil fuels and end this madness. Hey you, burning the Earth...we have had enough." Then an activist with a megaphone declared: "Barclays finances climate chaos: people are dying right now. The largest financier of fossil fuels in Europe". The chairman provisionally interrupted the meeting while the security guards expelled the protesters.

The intervention was a choral action that included other environmental organizations. On the same day, the protests continued in the surrounding streets with a satirical declamation from the organization Fossil Free London, who performed Shakespearean-style poems generated by Artificial Intelligence: "To be or not to be, that is the climate question." They accused the entity of being on the wrong side of history.

At the same time, the Extinction Rebellion activists, through a statement, pointed out that recent reports from Greenpeace and the Rainforest Action Network revealed that, since 2016, Barclays was the bank in Europe that invested the most in fossil fuel projects, providing up to 190 billion dollars in funding since the 2015 Paris Agreement. According to Money Rebellion campaign spokesman Andrew Taylor, the aim was to denounce the company's greenwashing actions. Social activism coined this term to denounce propaganda practices in which green marketing is carried out in a deceptive way to promote the perception that an organization's products, objectives, or policies are respectful of the environment to increase its benefits.

Since 2019, environmental activism's actions, interventions, and mobilizations are becoming more frequent. However, as we can see, they are not traditional protests with banners and slogans. Environmental movements make their demands, claims, and complaints visible through **the combination of activism and art**. Next, we will analyze the origins of this political and social activism, what it seeks to make visible, and its characteristics. Then we will reflect on the **ARTivism** concept and how artistic languages are incredibly effective and helpful for environmental activism.

THE DECADE OF PROTESTS

In the last decade, simultaneous protests occurred in different countries: East-West; North-South; and different political systems. Especially, 2019 was the year of protests. In different streets of the world, from Chile to Hong Kong, citizens gathered to claim varied demands in their slogans and objectives.

These protests, added to those during the pandemic, closed a period of mobilizations that began with the revolutions of the Arab Spring in Egypt, the anti-austerity movement in Spain, and the *Occupy Wall Street* movement in the United States. Although each of these outbreaks had different and unique characteristics, they also reflected **more profound problems**. The reports of *Latinobarómetro*, an annual public opinion survey that collects nearly 20,000 interviews in 18 Latin American countries, show that from 2010 to the present, the levels of support for democratic institutions in Latin America have been declining. Support for government institutions, political parties, and even the democratic regime is falling.

At a global level, The Economist highlights in its latest reports a progressive deterioration in the perception of democracy. This trend has led many analysts, such as political scientist Larry Diamond, to discuss a democratic recession. And for others, like *Anne Applebaum*, author of *Twilight of Democracy*, to realize that the democratic world is old, cold, and tired.

In this context, a different political and social activism arose from the one we know up to now. It is the activism of a **disruptive nature**, with a **contagious and extraordinarily mobilizing energy**. Social networks were the channel that allowed a hyperconnected society to take over the streets in protests. This activism uses **the body as a medium for dissent and technology to empower the voice**. Combine public space and social networks. In addition, it proposes a new type of organization: an organic and decentralized network that moves away from the traditional hierarchical structure. It has a solid local impact but with a global, transnational dimension, where creativity and content take precedence over any other consideration.

This activism is also characterized by the **youth component**, especially millennials (1981-1999) and centennials (1999-2005). More and more, young people are taking the lead to expose some of the political causes that most concern them: climate change, equality, gender, and socioeconomic gaps, the rights of migrants, etc. And they, with their initiatives, demonstrations, and protests, with the organization of movements worldwide, are actively participating in public life. They mobilize for causes in which they believe, convene, and challenge outside the political parties. The slogans are not carried out by an organization. There are no organizational or party flags. The leadership is choral, not directed.

ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIVISM AND ARTIVISM

The protests and social demonstrations that have played an enormous role in recent years are those linked to climate change. Since 2019, environmental collectives have been protesting like never before. In 2020, for example, the young activists found a way to continue demonstrating beyond the pandemic and confinement. That year, in Berlin, the Fridays For Future collective exhibited their banners in front of the Parliament in Berlin (and others in Europe) as a new way of intervening in public space. The images went viral in an instant.

Global warming is an undeniable reality and goes hand in hand with the rise in climate awareness on a global scale. According to a study by Amnesty International, youth are the ones who discuss the most about the need to do something to address the environmental challenge.

A survey of 10,000 young people from 22 countries reveals that they perceive climate change as the main problem in the world. According to Eurobarometer measurements, almost a third of Europeans say they have taken action to combat climate change in the last six months. And according to studies by the Pew Research Center, one in 10 Americans claims to have voluntarily participated in activities related to this issue, of which 32% are members of Generation Z (centennials).

After the pandemic, the protesters returned to the streets, but the novelty is that the leadership was not only from environmental organizations. They summoned, organized, and mobilized. But on the roads, a common cause that began to awaken awareness and involvement goes beyond those who have been working in the environmental cause was perceived.

The appearance of the activist Greta Thunberg on the public scene has been fundamental in **modifying the public debate regarding climate change**. Her audacity, effectiveness, and simplicity in her messages motivated important sectors of citizens worldwide to action.

Activist environmentalism has also hybridized with other causes seeking points of connection, such as feminism, anti-racist and anti-xenophobic movements, or the fight for equality, for LGTBI+ rights and the rights of migrants. All of them are causes that maintain contact links significantly and have been part of this enormous mobilizing capacity of political causes in the last decade.

These movements are mutually nourished by **exploring activism with a fertile renewal of formats through artistic languages**. In the book *"ARTivismo. El poder de los lenguajes artísticos para la comunicación política y el activismo"* ("ARTivismo. The power of artistic languages for political communication and activism"), Antoni Gutiérrez-Rubí argues that these activisms use the aesthetic plasticity of the arts (performing, literary, plastic, among others) **to awaken, inform, encourage and mobilize the people**. Hence, the word **ARTivism (art + activism)** and its outstanding contribution to social struggles. ARTivism transforms protests into creative demands, that is, not only fair ideas or demands but also has a creative dimension. Currently, environmental activism and feminism are at the forefront of these practices.

According to Gutiérrez-Rubí, ARTivism is characterized by being:

1. **Festive.** On many occasions, activist practices are fun. It aims to provoke **a creative laugh, joy, which is at the same time a complaint**. In 2019, when COP-25 was held in Madrid, Extinction Rebellion activists turned one of the city's main streets, La Gran Vía street, into an impromptu party and a massive protest. Flags with images of animals and colorful banners with messages such as "This is change"; "Climate and ecological emergency"; "Care"; "Now or never", were carried by the protesters, as well as drawn on their bodies giving color to the event. Meanwhile, music and dances filled the streets of the city center. They called it disobedience because they aimed to protest with music and dance.
2. **Coral.** They are citizen movements around the world that are empowering and prove that they want to decide, influence, and act... showing their capacity for coordination, communication, and visibility.
3. **On/off.** Actions that are considered a network developed in the public space, expanded online and generated links, relationships, transnational and transgressive alliances from the streets to the networks and from the networks to the streets.
4. **Hybrid.** Many languages, many formats, and many interventions. It is imperfect and diverse. The traditional borders of aesthetic or artistic protagonism are dissolved. The protagonists are people who use artistic language.
5. **Global.** Local interventions are strongly connected or inspired by international experiences with a global vocation.

The challenge for environmental movements is to continue placing the issue of climate change on the public agenda and mobilize citizens. To do this, the way is to continue challenging through disruptive, emotional, and mobilizing actions. **If the goal is to shake consciences, ARTivism is the way. It must be moved to mobilize.**

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SIDE B: THE MUSIC OF THE FIGHT FOR EARTH

By Adrián Fernández Reyes

On June 28, 2008, three prominent Icelandic music figures, Björk, Sigur Rós, and Ólaf Arnalds, shared the stage to protest to the Icelandic government over a program to build dams to generate electrical energy that would feed various aluminum smelting furnaces. Around 30,000 people attended the Náttúra concert; that is, 10% of the population of Iceland. Some years later, on May 3, 2014, on a tour of the Ecuadorian Amazon, René Pérez –better known as Residente– showed the media his oil-smeared hand after inserting it into the Aguarico 4 Well that, along with other hundreds of wells, was abandoned by the Chevron oil company twenty years ago. Hours later, the Calle 13 group appeared at the stadium in the province of Sucumbíos to give the concert “Por el aguante de Lago Agrio” (for the survival of the Agrio Lake), in which Residente, in his role as vocalist, called on the Ecuadorian people to continue the fight against Chevron-Exxon for the environmental degradation that it caused.

The collective organization and its different forms of protest constitute a tool to change reality. In general terms, this is the activism that the novelist Alice Walker defines in a way that makes the skin goosebumps by saying that “*activism is the rent that must be paid for living on the planet.*”

Of course, art is not a complete stranger to activism, hence the existence of the concept of artivism: a mixture of art and activism. Art has taken a predominant role as a political instrument throughout history, and through its various manifestations, it suggests that reality not only exists but is intentionally constructed through commitment, struggle, resistance, and rebellion. Art frees; it is a political act, a language of independence, and a form of storytelling that comes alive with strokes, shapes, colors, body movements, notes, and rhythms. In addition, art transgresses, vibrates, seeks resonance frequencies, and incites action and individual and collective transformation. The groups of artists seek to address injustices and socio-environmental challenges through music, film, photography, murals, performances, happenings, and other artistic expressions. In this article, I will focus on music.

Music can be compelling and thriving because of its tremendous reach. Sound waves -textually and symbolically- reach very far as a channel for transforming reality. Some radio stations in Mexico still tend to include, before the start of programs, expressions such as "*transmitting with 25,000 watts of power.*" At the same time, digital media allow access to music through a click on a streaming platform anywhere in the world. Historically, the most notorious case as a form of activism has been the protest song, where artists such as Mercedes Sosa, Óscar Chávez, Amparo Ochoa, Silvio Rodríguez, Víctor Jara, Violeta Parra, Joan Baez, and Édith Piaf found an important space and echo. Thus, musical artivism offers a collective voice: a -literal- cry that catalyzes social change.

As for environmental artivism, the diversity of musical genres is extensive: the pop-rock of Maná, with "*¿Dónde jugarán los niños?*" ("Where will the children play?"); the rock of Bersuit Vergarabat, with "*Madre hay una sola*" ("Mother, you only have one"); or the vegan metal of Godeater or Arch Enemy. Reggae is also represented by Jimmy Cliff's "*Save our planet Earth*"; eco-metal, with Avakr; funk, with Jamiroquai, on his album *Emergency on Planet Earth*; alternative rock, with the Radiohead song "*Sail to the Moon (Brush the Cobwebs out of the sky)*"; or punk, with Bad Religion, through the song "*Kyoto Now!*" whose theme deals precisely with the Kyoto Protocol and the need to reduce the emission of greenhouse gases. Another recent activist act worth mentioning is the transformation of activist Greta Thunberg's essay *Our House is on Fire* into the song "*The 1975*" (performed by the band of the same name). This work encourages, with some style of Henry David Thoreau, to give a kind of civil disobedience to detonate interventions to care for the environment. Also, events such as the International Festival of Music and Environmental Action have been created, which function not only as artistic spaces to listen to music but also to open conversations such as the one held by Rubén Albarrán from Café Tacuba, with the Peoples' Front in Defense of the earth. Also, the constant presence of Greenpeace -which always travels with its aura of positive and negative criticism- at the mythical Glastonbury festival is an opportunity to express a position and criticism from music. In fact, the space known as Greenpeace Field has become a bastion for environmental artivism, where it has been claimed in various ways and moments: "**Take action: we need your voice.**"

Interestingly, although awareness of environmental aspects is one of the axes that guides the artistic work of various bands, the groups necessarily come from different origins, have specific goals, and exhibit a particular ideology. I will briefly use the example of some "metalhead" environmental activists (including Wolves in the Throne Room, Panopticon, Agalloch, Velvet Cacoon, etc.) for whom, with their bushy beards and black robes, green is the new black. Wolves in the Throne Room was conceived by brothers Aaron and Nathan Weaver during a protest by the radical environmental group Earth First! His music and lyrics address the protection of the environment from an eco-spiritual conscience of Cascadia: a bioregionalist and independence movement that seeks the secession of the Cascadia region, in the Northwest of the United States, under ecological, cultural, political, and economic arguments.

Two other brothers, Mario and Joe Duplantier, members of Gojira, the important French progressive metal band, focus on themes about the accumulation of garbage on the planet and the damage to the forests. On the other hand, the Brazilian band Sepultura has groove metal and heavy metal songs that make visible the deforestation and global warming that affects the Amazon. For example, their song "Ambush" is a tribute to environmental activist Chico Mendes, who was assassinated for opposing the interests of corporations that wanted to continue extractivism in the Amazon jungle.

THE OTHER SIDE OF VINYL

It's not all good news, unfortunately. Backstage some events occur that should not go unnoticed. It is worth mentioning at this moment the zoologist Barry Commoner, who said that 1) everything is connected to everything else, 2) everything must go somewhere, and 3) there is no such thing as a free lunch. Regarding these last points, it is estimated that platforms such as Spotify or Apple Music emit between 200 and 350 million kilograms of greenhouse gases annually. Another example is the Live Earth that Al Gore organized in 2007 (a series of 11 concerts in the United Kingdom, the United States, South Africa, Brazil, Australia, Japan, Germany, and China), which was intended to attract an estimated audience of 2 billion of people to stop global warming and to encourage the transition to renewable energy. Of course, massive concerts generate a notable amount of atmospheric emissions, so there is an essential paradox in generating environmental awareness through this medium since the needs and ecological footprint of logistics, stages, equipment, staff, flights, lighting, and fireworks at events are remarkable.

Should massive concerts with environmental themes be avoided? Does it generate more impact to carry them out or not? We can count their carbon footprint, but measuring these events' positive and negative effects is not so easy. The mythical Live Aid concert was the worst case -at the risk of straying slightly from the central theme. That great concert on July 13, 1985, in which Freddie Mercury - in his iconic outfit of blue jeans and a white sleeveless shirt - was cheered by 72,000 spectators at Wembley. Much has been said about that event's possible successes or failures; it is considered the most influential benefit concert in history. According to its organizer, Bob Geldof, the event had a huge impact because the lingua franca is rock 'n' roll: it raised £150 million to help end hunger in Ethiopia. It set the tone for fundraising events through music. However, this welfare concept has its consequences, to say the least, and there are other more painful truths: apparently, a significant percentage of the profits went directly into the pockets of "the powerful" in Ethiopia, led by the dictator Mengistu Haile Mariam, who with that money bought weapons to subjugate his opponents.

Due to these situations, it is more difficult to measure the impact of these activist events, although indeed, the most appropriate path is not one of assistance but one that ensures a deeper understanding of the aspects that underlie the causes and consequences of socio-environmental problems.

After this digression and returning to the central theme of the emissions generated in musical events, *Music Declares Emergency* has been formed, a collective of artists and professionals from the music industry who have enlisted to call for the protection of all forms of life on Earth. Foals, Massive Attack, The xx, Savages, and many other bands and artists have come together under the banner "No music on a dead planet." They have focused on being more conscious about how they plan logistics and the concerts themselves. It begins to be more and more regular that green musical tours exist. For example, Coldplay's Music of Spheres tour was conceptualized under three principles to achieve a "sustainable tour": reduce, reinvent, and restore. The 2000 Trees Festival appropriated the "green, ethical, and musical" motto. The event was designed to respond to the vast music festivals that wanted to make money at all costs. At that festival, local musicians were hired to avoid transportation costs, and all food and drink were produced locally and placed in appropriate containers for recycling. It is also worth mentioning the Reverb Foundation, an NGO that works with music professionals -Maroon 5, Dave Matthews Band, Shawn Mendes, Billie Eilish, etc.- to reduce the environmental impact of their tours, through local catering, less staff for each concert, use of rechargeable batteries in monitors, lighting with clean energy, waste management and reduction in the use of single-use materials. In particular, Billie Eilish has implemented eco-villages at each of her concerts to raise awareness and educate about climate change. In addition, an excellent way to take advantage of her fame is that, on her tours, the sale of drinks in plastic containers will be prohibited, and she will request that water dispenser modules be available. Visualizing these strategies in some places is definitely challenging, but perhaps it will work as an incentive to start the transformations of massive music events. Of course, the effects of these actions alone might not be so considerable, and some might qualify these positions and activities as green-washing. Still, it is also true that each one of these artists is doing activist work from their space of action, its influences, and its ideology. They start with their truth and their particular way of raising their voices to reach others.

Artivism can transform our world and our reality by exchanging messages of desolation for hope; with awareness of the significant socio-environmental problems and challenges, or by creating alliances with other entities to be stronger. The poet and writer Allen Ginsberg once told Patti Smith, a leading musical exponent, and activist in the punk movement: "Be an artist, but also an activist." Fortunately, there always seems to be some voice listening to the music. For example, Patti Smith's debut album, *Horses*, had a substantial impact on Michael Stipe, who would later become the lead singer of R.E.M.

Finally, I want to introduce a second and last digression to this text, which has to do with the names of the songs. I have always found enigmatic and attractive the songs in whose name there is a parenthesis. Sometimes there were no agreements regarding the names, and the two best options were placed. At other times, the impression is that the information in parentheses suggests a complementary idea or that, in fact, it is the very spirit of the song or the motive that led to its creation. Three songs that include parentheses in their name and that coincide with intending to raise awareness about environmental problems are "*Mercy Mercy Me (The Ecology)*" by Marvin Gaye, "*Mother Earth (Natural Anthem)*" by Neil Young, and "*Sonic Forest (Déjame respirar)*" by Bomba Estéreo. I definitely do not know the interpretation that each of the authors gave to the texts in parentheses. Still, I know that if artivism is one of the transformation tools that guide our path toward a more sustainable one, I can be calm about the coming future. I can sum it up precisely by borrowing the title of one of R.E.M.'s songs (and let's not forget the text in parentheses), "It's the End of the World as We Know It (And I Feel Fine)."

Generally, an artist act requires participation, visibility, and public or virtual space. Non-musicians have also been involved in many artist strategies: for example, in planning and executing flash mobs and other events that use music as a creative and persuasive channel of expression, but also with something as simple as spreading music-themed songs of environmental care.

The Punto Crítico team has created a collaborative list of environmental artivism songs you can find in the *Take Away* section. Of course, you can collaborate in its expansion, share it, and join this artist act.

C₂ONVERSING

From the graph to the canvas

Interview with **Jill Pelto**
by **Jazmín Mota y**
Mariana Velázquez

Raising awareness about the challenges we, as humanity, face is at the core of many conversations and audiences, from parliaments to schools, from corporate board meetings to casual dinners with friends and family. However, occasionally, the message remains in the news headlines as an abstract concept that seeks to permeate from a dialogue to a deeper, engaging, and motivating state that effectively triggers actions that take us into more sustainable, sympathetic, and just trajectories. But what happens when we find a way to connect facts with our emotions? In fact, this is one of the things that Jill Pelto's artwork does.

Jill Pelto is an Artist and a Science Communicator currently based in Richland, Washington. She grew up in Massachusetts, lived in Maine for a decade, and New Mexico briefly. Her work focuses on communicating human-environment connections by incorporating scientific data directly into her paintings to engage broad audiences with climate change graphs. She is passionate about outreach and collaboration.

Jill completed a Masters of Science at the University of Maine and B.A. degrees in Studio Art and Earth Science. She has researched the sensitivity of the Antarctic Ice Sheet to changes, the mountain glaciers of Washington and British Columbia, the Dry Valleys and Transantarctic Mountains of Antarctica, the Falkland Islands, and New Zealand.

Jz: Jill, please tell us about your story. How did you become both an artist and a scientist?

Jill: I think I was born with a love of art, it was always a part of my life, and I started getting serious about it. As a teenager, I knew I wanted to study art, and the science part was a mix of caring about and loving the outdoors and learning natural sciences. Many of the ways I learned about that was from my parents because they have natural sciences backgrounds. That was really inspiring. At the end of college, I came up with the idea of incorporating data of different types into my paintings.

I was trying to find a way to communicate with people and tell a story. I wanted to make science research more accessible, and having that emotional side of art was such a big piece of it. I wanted people to think: "Oh, this is what this feels like and why this matters!". The data can be seen like a line, so I want people to feel why that line matters. Then, I realized art could help with that. I try to have a mix of emotions or stories in my paintings more now in a way I didn't really think about at the beginning.

Rather than overwhelm people, I also want to show things that are hopeful and show action. It's been a bit harder for me to figure out how to show that, partly because there are a lot of positive changes happening, but not necessarily represented with data. I've been figuring out what stories will connect with people and how I can use my art even beyond getting people thinking. So, I do a lot of stuff with schools and some community workshops. I try to make it accessible in different ways. I really enjoy it. That's a big piece that I'm trying to connect.

Jz: So, how can you go one step forward in engaging people with what you do?

Jill: The main thing I do, and have been doing for a long time, is work with kids of different ages and going as a guest to schools. Basically, I have them make their own science art. I work with the teacher and bring in graphs related to what the kids have been learning in science that year. Or if not, it's stuff like "*Here's how the temperature is rising in this state!*" or "*Here's how we're using renewable energies.*" I find a range of topics for the students to make art about. I've done that with many schools, mainly in the USA, but some outside. When I see the final work, I find it inspiring to see how many of them can understand what they think about these topics. I show them this blend and how we can use art to tell stories about important things we care about.

When working with adults or in a community of a mix of any age, it is like giving a talk or an art show at a gallery or coffee shop or whatever it is. For one event, I brought a bunch of graphs about the specific town the event was in. And I worked with the community to get that data about energy use in many of the town's buildings. It was information you would only sometimes see. It was simple local data that most people, including myself, would never see. Then people could make art with that data at the event. The point wasn't to make a good piece of art; it was just to get them thinking and talking about it and create that purposeful space. Because many people need more time and energy in their day to think about climate change or stay up to date about what's happening. I think when you create a specific space, whether online or in person, for people to just engage for a little bit and feel comfortable doing so either to do a piece of art or just talking about environmental stuff locally, it opens up the space for a conversation.

Another thing that can play into that is if we can go outside to learn about things hands-on before we go back to a dedicated space for working with students or communities so that we can engage with the topic. The hardest part of this kind of work is to figure out how to do these things and find funding for them.

Jz: I feel that scientific data seems far from the "common" people but restricted to a group of "experts." Could art change how we connect otherwise cold and distant data with the real world and our lives?

Jill: I think it can be for many people; we all have different interests and learning strengths. It's obviously going to only connect with some. Sometimes, if someone looks at a graph, they don't really know, even after reading the description, what it's saying. Often they can understand if they do engage with it further, but many people need to. That's why the art is that emotional part getting them to feel why these data matter and think about it in their own lives. I believe that emotional reactions can be more powerful and lasting to people.

When I'm working with groups of scientists, I see to them there's so much emotion and care behind their research and what they are doing. That is why I've been trying to collaborate with them to communicate what they do.

Because sharing their work in the scientific community is excellent, but it will take a lot of work to get through to the average person.

Jz: We are talking about a new language that can help translate science into something more attainable to most people. And you have mentioned the emotions that I consider at the core of our motivations, close to our hearts. Do you have any particular piece of your artwork that is very relevant to you or close to your heart?

Jill: Yeah, I think a few of my recent artworks, I could describe two of them. One is about the research I've been doing with my dad since I was a teenager. Basically, we work on the mountain glaciers here, where I now live in Washington State. The glaciers are significant for the region and the ecosystem. A lot of the water from the ice and the glaciers helps feed the streams, rivers, and lakes, but the glaciers are getting much smaller. My dad started a project as a Ph.D. student; this is the 40th year of his research, and I work on the project with him. So, I made a piece of art that shows the graph of how the glaciers are getting smaller over time. I tell the story about the changes I have seen and how dramatic they are.

For the other pieces, I made two big paintings; they go side by side in a diptych. They are meant to be paired. They are for my first inclusion in a museum show. They are about sea level rise on the East Coast of the United States. I was showing sea level rise in salt marsh ecosystems and how there are things that people are trying to do to protect or preserve them. I was trying to tell this complex story of a specific ecosystem affected by sea level rise. Those are the stories I would like to tell more in different places in the world.

Jz: Do you have any messages to share with our readers regarding the power of matching art and science to take action and face the current challenges of nature and human interactions?

Jill: I think it could be cool if there was a community or school in Mexico, or somewhere else, just having students do an activity around making environmental art. No matter what type of art you're doing. Giving students a chance to turn whatever they are learning about any topic in school into a piece of art can help them to express what they are learning and what they're interested in and worried about.

You can connect it with what you're learning about in interdisciplinary projects because students have different learning strengths. So, for students who are really into art but not science, it allows them to engage with a particular topic differently.

And then, in terms of adults and communities, galleries or restaurants or libraries or any public spaces can serve for hosting an art show or exhibition that could also include some scientists at it to share information that is relevant to the community. Implementing interdisciplinary art and science is a way to make scientific knowledge more accessible to people and have that emotional side of science.

Visit Jill's website to learn more about her and her artwork.

<https://www.jillpelto.com/>

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Cuento

PRANA

Autora: **Iliana Muñoz**

White, all white. Wherever you look, there is no end. Its immensity makes it impossible for the image to be caught in something, not a photo, not a video, not a painting, not a word, of course, not a theater. Only presence and in it disbelief for the foreigner, custom for the local. Why do we try to make art as a container of nature? When we try to catch "this," we fail.

I've been in the truck for miles, head cocked to the window, surprised that I'm here, that this is real. There are only two colors, white and blue; blue reaches different tones but always toward the light, toward crystalline. The white is impeccable because it has no contact with humans, except for its eyes, which cannot get all this snow dirty. We are supposed to get somewhere, this is just the journey, but the journey itself is already an experience. Experience the new word that capitalism wastes to sell moments and not things.

From the moment I stood at the plane's door to start going down the stairs leading to the runway, I knew I had arrived at a different place. The air is made of another material born from another place. Your nose makes you question if you are on another planet. I took a deep breath to gauge its quality in the lungs and store a little in memory, even though keeping reserves of something like that is impossible. It is unlike the sea jet stored in a 600ml PET bottle.

The air can make you sick or relieve you. As a child, I had asthma; for the asthmatic, the air is always an absence, but sometimes the crisis came from excess, tickling, and intense laughter; it was forbidden to have too much fun. Once, we went near Popo, to the slopes, in one of my father's vans, with a closed cargo shed. It was the first time I heard that about the slopes of a volcano; it made me laugh. I was behind with my brother, playing indeed. I don't know when they got on; I just remember having them as companions, a couple of peasants to whom my father gave a ride. They carried pieces of firewood; they had an intense smell, new to me, both they and the wood.

The smell of wood, trees, and trapped air, made me sick—shortness of breath, wheezing in my chest, and no Salbutamol inhaler in my backpack. Snow in the distance, white, cold, my mom worried about me again, overprotective, internally blaming the wind, my dad, the stowaways, anything, for my illness.

Iceland: Land of Fire and Ice. It is said that when two opposing concepts overlap in the mind, the body reacts with laughter. Fire-Ice, Skirt-Volcano. The immense bodies of thermal water on this island, like natural embraces amid the freezing cold, do not make me laugh but enchantment and bewilderment. I wonder why they exist. Who designed it that way? I wonder as much as a relative asks with pain during grief: "Why did he die, why now?" With the same desire to know, with the same absent response, unless one accumulates mystical arguments.

We got to where we had to go, the Glacier Lagoon. How far did we travel? Four hours, five, I don't know. What is extraordinary for us tourists is every day for our driver-guide. All the way, he has tried to talk to us without anyone having seconded him. He let me go ahead for traveling alone. She chose me over the other solo traveler, a handsome Russian—an advantage for me, a privileged view, and greater comfort. But I was not a good co-pilot—neither me nor anyone of the eight behind.

The guide-driver tried to get words out of a mailbox. We all remained too absorbed in our thoughts, in sleeping and using the driver as a driver, not as a company. He also tried another strategy, a monologue instead of questions. He told us that he had studied for eight intensive months to be a guide, knew everything there was to know, and had passed the exams with flying colors. No one praised him, no one condescended, no one challenged his knowledge, no one played his game of trying to pronounce the difficult Icelandic names: "Eyjafjallajökull, Jökulsárlón, come on, try... Jö-kul" no one nothing. We just wait through the whiteness until we reach the glaciers.

For a moment, I wondered whether humans had the right to be there. Humans can be stubborn and persevering. Legend has it that a Norwegian Viking came to settle in Iceland to flee his crime, a murder. The beginnings of sedentary life in that land are confusing, contradictory, vague, full of stories of crime-flight-persecution-supernatural events. The Norwegian Viking who fled to Iceland sent in an almost magical act two wooden sticks so that they would show him where to settle. Wood determined Reykjavik. There he stayed with his family... and they lived happily ever after and had offspring that today provide tourist services to other less foolish but more curious humans.

A British tourist in the van announces that he has a question. The driver-guide's excitement at knowing that someone is finally interested in his knowledge vanishes in a snort when he hears the question: "Why on all this land, so large, aren't there more human settlements, more houses?" The answer to that is easy, hence the frustration of the guide who expected a challenge and not something so obvious: "This is all a volcanic zone. At any moment, the eruption of a volcano would end any attempt at civilization.

Despite nature's warnings, there we humans are, coexisting, taking photos in front of the geysers, bathing in the hot springs, hunting the northern lights. The night before, I went with a smaller group to try to see blue-green wonders in the sky, we failed, but the trip was shorter, more intimate, with more sounds of disappointment uttered collectively: "Mmmm, boo, ajjjjj."

Human beings chase each other, we chase whales, we chase turtles, we chase butterflies, we chase northern lights, we chase sharks, we chase orcas, we chase dolphins, we chase mushrooms, we chase tigers, we chase elephants, we chase ducks, we chase volcanoes, we chase water, we chase star showers, we chase ruins, we chase passport stamps, we chase radiation remnants, we chase fossils, we chase cave paintings, we chase sunrises, we chase sunsets, we chase constellations, we chase vaccines, we chase white moons, we chase full moons, we chase red moons, we chase eclipses, we chase mountain peaks, we chase sacred rivers, we chase freedom, we chase shamans, we chase beliefs, we chase forbidden drugs, we chase offers, we chase other people's rituals, we chase experiences, we chase pilgrimage routes, we chase saints, we chase adrenaline, we chase serotonin, we chase ends of the world, we chase planets, we chase crossing off lists to do while death chases us, we chase postponements of the cessation of breathing...

While my eyes are lost in the whiteness of the glaciers, while I see pieces of ice floating, while I register a shade of light blue that I did not know, while I hear a tourist complain to his wife and say: "this is not my thing, this is contemplative, I am adventurous," my mind betrays me and takes me out of the moment, to make me remember when I went to see blue whales in Mirisa, in Sri Lanka. Darya didn't want to go with me; he said it was because he thought she was horrible. I believe that, once again, it was because he did not want to pay; if it had been free, he would have gone. I woke up very early and did what some more remote internet forums advised, not to buy the high ticket price online and go to the pier in the morning to negotiate with those of the boats. I did, and it worked—a foreign young single woman. Within minutes I had a half-price ticket online, an exclusive spot on the bow, and a male staff member "watching" me.

After the boat, I was on and others, all competing with each other, spent a lot of time chasing whales, I realized how pathetic it was; it wasn't even worth it for free. The boats were tilting badly, looking frail and hopeless, all the passengers wearing orange vests, all a bunch of idiots breaking into the whales' habitat. The drivers of the boats received constant notifications from others who, in smaller boats, watched the path of the whales and indicated where to go. And we, dragged by ambition and the search for the photo, went there, accelerating, losing control of the aquatic vehicles.

Some people began to despair; others became dizzy, vomited, and sudden emotion to see just the fin of a whale. We got to see a family of whales swim past us, surrounded by about fifteen flimsy boats, each with dozens of people, repulsive, sad. I would have liked to vomit along with the Asian next to me, pale, living a nightmare, but my breaths and the eucalyptus Ayurvedic inhaler I was carrying had stabilized my stomach. I couldn't expel the disgust that entered my eyes through my mouth.

Back in the truck, after having taken photos of the glaciers and having contemplative moments, memories of the past, and existential questions, it was when I had the clear notion that the Icelandic tour guide, in his frustration, wanted to kill us. He no longer made an effort to speak; he had given up; his hands gripped the steering wheel furiously; he was going very fast, he was breathing heavily, his gaze was fixed on the terrifying whiteness ahead. We had become his prey.

I couldn't sleep anymore, waiting for the moment when the man swerved a bit and crashed us into something or turned the truck over. I felt compassion, forced compassion, belated compassion for repentance. If I hadn't put my headphones on to create my selfish sonic atmosphere, if we had listened to him, if we had enjoyed each other's company, if we had done one of those repetitive roadside group chants, this man wouldn't be about to commit suicide and multiple homicide.

He will kill us; he will kill himself because it is not true that he loves his work; he has seen the same natural wonders thousands of times, three out of seven days a week. The glaciers have frozen his expectations, the attractions of his country no longer take his breath away, he is fed up, he is tired of girls who travel while they study for their master's degree, of the "lovely" of the British, of gringas playing at being Barbie newlyweds, tired of not understanding Chinese diction, fed up with absent Finns and Russians with glacier-colored eyes. He he he tried and tried, and we didn't care.

Iceland has from zero to one murder per year. This contrast made me laugh, we were about to become history, to change the statistics, but I would rather be a living being ignored than a dead person on the front page. Would a well-intentioned, very focused joint prayer help? I don't know; in this truck, we must have Catholics, agnostics, Buddhists, Orthodox, Protestants... We will die from a lack of joint intonation, from a lack of empathy, from an excess of hubris. It was about to get dark; winter in Iceland falls very early, daylight would fade, white would take on another color, and perhaps this man's thoughts would become more cloudy, or maybe he would calm down, thinking that there was less time left to get home and enjoy of the hot dinner prepared by his wife. Did he have a wife? We didn't pay attention when he tried to tell us...

Installation

MB>CO₂: A Dystopian Art Experience Unmasking the Hidden CO₂ Emissions from AI Models Like ChatGPT

Author: Thijs Biersteker, 2022

The MB>CO₂ art installation by ecological artist Thijs Biersteker is a captivating and immersive experience that delves into the environmental impact of data usage, mainly focusing on AI models like ChatGPT. Besides, the pandemic has driven up data consumption and associated CO₂ emissions.

The installation captures visitors' interactions with ChatGPT, monitoring data usage and calculating carbon footprints. In a visual display, CO₂ emissions are transformed into smoke puffs released into a living biotope. This representation emphasizes the urgency of adopting energy-efficient hardware, renewable energy sources in data centers, and the need for sustainable AI practices

As spectators engage in the installation, they witness how virtual interactions translate into real-world consequences. Each action's CO₂ emissions are meticulously calculated and visualized as puffs of smoke filling the living biotope. Reveals the hidden environmental impact of daily data usage. It serves as a call to action urging developers and users to mitigate the environmental impact of AI and data-intensive technologies.

Links:

<https://thijsbiersteker.com>

<https://thijsbiersteker.com/chatgpt-artwork-mbc02>

Instagram @thijs_biersteker

The small amounts of CO₂ that we generate from our daily activities can add up quickly and have a huge impact on the planet."

— Thijs Biersteker, artist

Illustration

Replanting Resilience

Author: **Jill Pelto, 2022 (Diptych)**

Replanting Resilience (Diptych) addresses how humans and natural habitats respond to shifting environmental conditions and climate adversity in the Gulf of Maine. The work draws inspiration from current actions being taken to restore the Great Marsh along coastal Massachusetts, such as re-planting marsh grass and monitoring the effects of sea level rise. Three line-graphs are incorporated, and they depict, from bottom to top:

- Historical sea level rise from 1950 to 2020 and projections for the future rise to 2050.
- Increase in National Wildlife Refuge acreage in Massachusetts, Maine, and New Hampshire from 2001 to 2020.
- Increase in the percentage of US adults who supported policies to protect the environment from 2008 to 2019.

Together, the data show how public mind-frames and efforts are rising to meet the tide—a story of how we can come together to act on what we know and feel.

Links

<https://www.jillpelto.com/resilience-12>

<https://www.jillpelto.com/>

PARA LLEVAR

TAKE-AWAY

Collaborative Playlist: *Punto Crítico* *ARTivism*

We share this collaborative list of environmental activism songs that the Punto Crítico team has prepared for you. Of course, we invite you to collaborate in its expansion and share it as an act of ARTivista.

<https://open.spotify.com/playlist/06w5JNPTv8XYDpCMFRHDy8?si=cc3f4777ab00495f&pt=c6d5a23d52373f52df8c0d1eaa7b7a5>

Theater play: *Pulmones (Lungs)*

In the context of a planet in the climate crisis, a young couple asks the question of an entire generation: Does it make sense to bring a new life to a screwed-up world? In the dialogues of this modern love story, the ideological conflicts of their young adulthood are seen until life passes them by and tests the foundations of their relationship.

<https://pulmonesmx.com/>

Video/Documentary: *Fighting Climate Change with Art*

This video reveals the works of Thijs Biersteker, an eco-artist, and guest of this Punto Crítico issue. You can learn more about his work, which seeks to raise awareness about the planet's situation by making visible problems such as climate change and environmental protection through interactive and immersive installations.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xfrC_tBSI_k

Book: *Generating science awareness about climate change: new perspectives from Mexico*

This book addresses the strategies to excite and raise awareness on this topic, and it is here where activism, scientific knowledge produced from the social sciences and ARTivism play a fundamental role.

<http://www.lacab.org.mx/index.php/publicaciones/libros-coordinados/114-generando-con-ciencia-sobre-el-cambio-climatico-nuevas-miradas-desde-mexico>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

Book: *Artivismo. El poder de los lenguajes artísticos para la comunicación política y el activismo (Artivism. The power of artistic languages for political communication and activism)*

This book by Antoni Gutiérrez-Rubí presents ARTivism as the expression of a new politics derived from the change in the relationship between rulers and citizens in a volatile context where people find new ways to express their demands. You can find more information about the book in the following link:

<https://www.gutierrez-rubi.es/2021/02/11/libro-artivismo-el-poder-de-los-lenguajes-artisticos-para-la-comunicacion-politica-y-el-activismo/>

Video: *Communicating Science through Art - Jill Pelto*

In this video, you will learn more about the work of Jill Pelto, our interviewee for this issue. Learn more about her passion for communicating science through her illustrations in a simple and engaging way to raise awareness and voices around climate change issues.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2N_owj-dj-LM

Exhibition: *MODTHERN NATURE*

It is a multi-sensory installation that takes biodiversity and the transformation of the Pedregal as a starting point as a result of modern thought. The objective of this exhibition is that through art, it can be explored as fields of experimentation, research and knowledge, taking into account the immediate context and creating connections between living beings, places and cultures.

<https://arteabierto.org/gabrielagalvan-micrositio/>

Course: *Introduction to Sustainability in the Extractive Industry*

This online course consists of 5 modules through which you will learn the basic concepts of sustainability in relation to the extractive industry (mining, hydrocarbons, water, etc.) to build a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between the activities carried out in this industry and socio-ecosystems. The course is available through the ENERYOU platform:

<https://elearning.eneryou.org/products/Introducci%C3%B3n%20a%20la%20Sostenibilidad%20en%20la%20Industria%20Extractiva>

Mexico City, Mexico, 2023